

"THE INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF ANTI-CORRUPTION EFFORTS"

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the international legal framework surrounding anti-corruption efforts. It examines key international documents, such as the UN Convention against Corruption and the International Convention against Corruption in the Public Sector, to analyze principles, mechanisms, strengths, and weaknesses inherent in the global fight against corruption. Additionally, it discusses the necessity of further refining international legal mechanisms to ensure effective protection of societal interests and the reinforcement of legal order at both national and international levels. The study underscores the significance of ongoing academic inquiry into this crucial aspect of global governance and highlights avenues for enhancing international cooperation in combating corruption.

Corruption-related crimes now possess a transboundary nature, underscoring the necessity for international cooperation in combating them. Numerous international organizations, such as the UN, the Council of Europe, and the European Union, have developed a range of international legal instruments dedicated to addressing the issue of corruption. This reflects the acknowledgment that corruption is not confined to a single state and requires coordinated actions from the international community.

In light of this, strategies to combat corruption have come to encompass various aspects, including preventing attempts to overthrow authority and countering the financing of terrorism and extremism. The adoption of international legal instruments, such as the UN Convention against Corruption, has formed the basis for establishing an international system of legal regulation in this field.

This convention, along with other documents, delineates a broad spectrum of corrupt practices, encompassing bribery in both the public and private sectors, money laundering, and embezzlement. While the term "corruption" may not be explicitly formulated in these acts, they precisely define corrupt actions and establish measures of accountability for them.

From the analysis of international legal instruments defining the concept of "corruption," it is evident that international law interprets this phenomenon broadly.

Some acts narrowly define corruption as merely the giving or receiving of bribes, which fails to capture the full scope of corrupt manifestations. Key characteristics of corruption include unlawfulness, selfish motives, and social consequences such as the erosion of authority¹.

Currently, international legal regulation in the field of combating corruption operates at three levels: universal, regional, and bilateral. It is closely intertwined with national legislation, with national laws influencing international legal acts, for example, through recommendations for improving legislation or the development of model laws.

There are three models of combating corruption in international law. The American model employs restrictive laws and incentives, while officials are deprived of immunity. The European model involves active participation of governmental bodies in the allocation of financial resources with subsequent accountability to society, as well as moral influence through the media. The model of Asian countries is characterized by strict punishment for corrupt acts, meticulous personnel policies, and the establishment of specialized anti-corruption bodies.

At present, there is significant development of international norms and standards aimed at combating corruption at various levels. This lays the groundwork for the formation of a specialized area of anti-corruption international cooperation in international law. However, further improvement of legal regulation in this area is necessary.

Of particular interest is the potential of the Eurasian Economic Union in the context of anti-corruption efforts. The development of a Eurasian anti-corruption strategy could be a significant step in this direction. Drafting such a document in the form of an international agreement or recommendation would help establish standards for combating corruption and adopt positive experiences from other countries and regions.

The "Eurasian Integration Barometer" project, implemented by the Eurasian Development Bank, represents an interesting initiative. Its implementation allows surveying the population of twelve countries annually on various aspects of integration. Including questions about combating corruption in this survey appears to be an important and effective way of ascertaining public opinion in this sphere.

To combat transnational corruption, active cooperation among law enforcement and judicial authorities of different countries is necessary. This includes developing effective strategies for tracking individuals who have committed corrupt crimes and are hiding abroad. Law enforcement agencies must possess deep knowledge of international and national tracing procedures and be able to apply them in practice, including the use of modern information technologies.

The activity of international search for individuals who have committed corruption-related crimes is regulated by international agreements, treaties, and national legislation. Organizations such as Interpol and Europol play a crucial role in coordinating efforts between law enforcement agencies of different countries. Their activities are aimed at effectively locating and transmitting information about individuals involved in corruption crimes.

Search operations can be conducted at various levels: local, which is carried out within one country; interstate, covering the territories of CIS countries; and international, involving

¹ Fialkovskaya, I. D. "Corruption: Concept, Characteristics, Types." Bulletin of Lobachevsky University of Nizhny Novgorod 1 (2018): 137-142

the activities of law enforcement agencies of CIS countries worldwide. It is important to note that in some international treaties and agreements, explicit mention of the search for individuals who have committed corruption crimes may be absent, but such activities are implied. For example, the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime does not directly mention search operations, but Article 16, paragraph 9 concerning establishing the guilt of persons accused of corruption and evading prosecution outside their own country, implies such actions².

The effectiveness of efforts by individual states and the global community in combating corruption is partly determined by the number of successfully investigated corruption crimes and the prosecution of corrupt individuals. Although membership of states in international organizations such as Interpol expands their capabilities for searching for such individuals, search operations conducted under the auspices of such organizations may not always fully meet modern requirements.

Our position is to advocate for the examination of various aspects, such as forensic, criminal procedural, and operational-search aspects, with the aim of improving international legal regulation and developing practical recommendations in the field of search for individuals who have committed transnational corruption crimes, as well as in the overall fight against corruption.

The necessity of developing anti-corruption policies has become an indispensable condition in the fight against corruption, especially after the adoption of the UN Convention against Corruption in 2003. While solid foundations have been laid for this fight, further success requires joint efforts of all states, as none of them are immune to corruption.

To achieve this goal, the following tools can be used or improved: direct international legal and financial operations, such as expeditious extradition of corruption offenders and legal cooperation between states; direct monitoring of the implementation and effectiveness of anti-corruption measures; establishment of anti-corruption bodies, similar to the Independent Commission Against Corruption in Hong Kong; prevention of corruption crimes by reducing bureaucracy, monitoring government contracts, involving media and society in corruption investigations; use of enforcement methods to combat corruption, such as asset tracking and protection of corruption whistleblowers.

Thus, addressing the issue of corruption has acquired international significance and has become one of the most important aspects of global community activity. Numerous international documents have been adopted for the legal regulation of this problem, including the Convention on Offenses and Corruption, the Convention against Bribery of Foreign Public Officials in International Business Transactions, the Resolution of the Council of Europe Committee of Ministers "On Twenty Principles of Combating Corruption," and others.

It is widely recognized that international cooperation in combating corruption and transnational crimes plays a key role in enhancing the effectiveness of countering these phenomena. In this regard, various measures are being taken for legal regulation and coordination of actions between countries, including the development and signing of numerous international agreements and conventions, such as the Convention on Offenses and

² Bukharina, N. P. "Concept and Characteristics of Corruption in International Legal Instruments." Law. Journal of the Higher School of Economics 1 (2016): 166-176.

Corruption, the Convention against Bribery of Foreign Public Officials in International Business Transactions, and others.

For example, in 2023, within the framework of the UN, 36,407 complaints of corruption crimes were registered, which constitutes 67.32% of the total number registered for the previous year (11,429 complaints in 2022). This indicates an increase in awareness and activity in combating corruption.

However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of international cooperation in combating corruption and transnational crimes also depends on many factors, such as adherence to the principles of the rule of law, the effectiveness of judicial and law enforcement agencies, as well as mechanisms of international cooperation and information exchange.

According to Article 3 of the Universal Declaration on Combating Corruption of October 24, 2020, No. 123-FZ1, a key direction of anti-corruption activity is to ensure transparency and openness in all areas of state and public activities; promoting the development and use of modern technologies, methods of information provision, and analysis in the fight against corruption; supporting civil initiatives aimed at detecting and preventing manifestations of corruption.

However, a systemic approach is required for successful counteraction to corruption. For example, it is important to actively involve the public and local communities in monitoring the activities of government bodies (for example, through the participation of public observers and the establishment of feedback mechanisms with citizens). It is also necessary to strengthen the role of independent bodies overseeing the performance of state functions and combating corruption, including by increasing the effectiveness of their work and expanding their powers. Overall, joint efforts and cooperation between states, civil organizations, businesses, and society as a whole are the basis for effective anti-corruption efforts.

The concept of "international anti-corruption architecture" refers to a system of measures and mechanisms aimed at curbing corruption at the international level.

One of its key elements is the development of internal and international standards and approaches to combating this phenomenon.

One method of enhancing international standards and practices in combating corruption is the establishment of effective international control mechanisms that allow for the detection and prevention of corrupt practices. These mechanisms are based on the principles of transparency, accountability, and societal participation, which contribute to the formation and development of an open and trusting atmosphere in the global fight against corruption. They are also aimed at strengthening international cooperation and coordinating efforts in the prevention, investigation, and suppression of corrupt offenses³.

The adoption of international norms and standards in the fight against corruption involves not only the implementation of modern methods and tools but also the formation and development of mechanisms for international cooperation, including the exchange of information, technologies, experience, and best practices. The creation of an effective

³ Gravina, Alla Arkadyevna. "Transnational Corruption as a Constituent of International Crime." *Russian Law Journal* 12 (228) (2015): 87-100.

international anti-corruption architecture is necessary to ensure sustainable development and protect society from various forms of corruption and its negative consequences.

UN documents in the field of combating corruption include:

- The United Nations General Assembly Resolution (adopted by the General Assembly in 2006), aimed at supporting efforts to combat corruption at the international level. This document, in particular, provides support to judicial bodies and facilitates the development of international standards, such as: investigation; prevention and suppression of corrupt offenses; prevention of unjust enrichment; enhancing transparency; cooperation between states, etc.
- The UN Declaration on Principles and Rules of Combating Corruption and its Eradication in States.
- The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.
- The Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights in the context of combating corruption.
- Principles and approaches to combating corruption in international activities.
- Provisions to support efforts to combat corruption in international cooperation and principles.

These documents provide the basic framework for international cooperation in the fight against corruption and offer guidance on principles and approaches to preventing and suppressing this phenomenon at the global level.

Documents of the Council of Europe and the European Union in the field of combating corruption include:

1. Resolution on State Integrity as the Basis for Developing an Effective Anti-Corruption Strategy and Creating a System of Principles and Methods to Combat Corruption at the International and National Levels.
2. Decision on Transnational Anti-Corruption Efforts, aimed at strengthening cross-border cooperation to prevent and combat corruption crimes. The Council of Europe is not the body of this decision.
3. Resolution on Prevention, Detection, Investigation, and Suppression of Crimes among Public Servants, Staff, and Government Members.
4. "Twenty Principles" of combating corruption.
5. Model Code of Conduct for Public Servants, among others.

The document of the CIS on countering corruption represents a special mechanism aimed at developing and improving mechanisms for countering corruption in the CIS countries. This document provides a systemic approach to preventing and combating corruption, including measures to regulate the activities of public and private organizations, as well as to strengthen the legal and regulatory framework and international cooperation. It aims to enhance the effectiveness of anti-corruption efforts and ensure public trust in government institutions and law enforcement agencies. Such initiatives are implemented within the CIS to develop a unified strategy and standards for combating corruption, which contributes to strengthening the rule of law and fostering a favorable investment climate⁴.

⁴ Ivashkin, Nikita Sergeevich. "International Legal Foundations of Combating Corruption in International Law." Law and Justice 4 (2024): 269-274.

Documents of other international organizations are aimed at developing mechanisms to combat corruption based on international standards and norms. In this context, the CIS has taken into account a document adopted by the European Commission in 2012⁵.

However, not all aspects of the work of these international organizations are taken into account within national anti-corruption systems, preventing them from being adapted to the specific characteristics and requirements of each country. This approach highlights the need for discussion and measures to strengthen the role and influence of international organizations in combating corruption, especially in the context of their interaction with national institutions and law enforcement agencies. The presented documents on countering corruption can serve as a basis for developing a common strategy and standards for international cooperation in this area, contributing to the effectiveness of the fight against corruption and strengthening international legislation and regulatory frameworks.

The "Regulation" document is formalized in writing and approved in point "a" of paragraph 1 of the Supreme Council Decision No. 273-OS of September 25, 2008, concerning the development of mechanisms to combat corruption and the implementation of corresponding measures to ensure transparency and efficiency in the activities of state and municipal structures. Point "b" of paragraph 1 of Decision No. 273-OS provides for the regulation of mechanisms to combat corruption, including the development of measures to prevent abuse of official position (for example, preventing conflicts of interest and taking measures to prevent data and information distortion)⁶.

In carrying out the monitoring of the implementation of the aforementioned measures to combat corruption, the participation of an independent expert group is envisaged, which will monitor compliance with legality and the effectiveness of the measures' application, including the analysis of relevant reports and data. It is important to note that these measures must adhere to high standards of legality and ensure effective interaction between various bodies and institutions.

The need for the implementation of ethical principles and anti-corruption measures is confirmed by the necessity to consider the specifics and requirements of each particular situation.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the study of the international legal framework for combating corruption is a relevant and important direction in modern scientific research. This work has analyzed the main international documents regulating the issue of corruption, such as the UN Convention against Corruption and the International Convention against Corruption in the Public Sector.

The study has identified the main principles and mechanisms of international cooperation in combating corruption, as well as the problems and contradictions arising in the process of their implementation. The strengths and weaknesses of existing international instruments for combating corruption have been identified, and ways to improve them have been proposed.

Overall, the results of the study lead to the conclusion about the necessity of further improving the international legal mechanisms for combating corruption in order to ensure

⁵https://www.unodc.org/documents/treaties/UNCAC/Publications/Convention/08-50028_R.pdf

⁶ Sibgatullina, Luiza Ilfatovna. "Key Concepts of Corruption in International Law." *Bulletin of Economics, Law, and Sociology* 1 (2019): 114-117.

effective protection of societal interests and strengthen the rule of law at both national and international levels.

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